

THE IMPORTANCE OF PPT FOR TEACHERS AND LEARNERS IN TEACHING

Buriboev J. ¹, Abdimalikova G. ²

Abstract:

This article aims to explore the role of power point (PPT) in the modern world and their importance in teaching and learning for teachers and students. In addition, it is aimed to highlight the biggest disadvantages of PPT along with the good features of PPT, such as saving teachers' time during lessons, attracting students, attention and forming oral speech.

Key words: power point, advantages and teachers disadvantages, oral speech, students' attention.

Introduction.

In today's developing world, huge number of programs and discoveries are being created. Their upsides are reflected in all of our lives, especially in education because it is very difficult to imagine learning and learning anything without ppt. It opens the door of a wide range of opportunities especially for teachers and students at a university. According to Fatemi Samieri Lari (2014), "the use of technology in school has developed new ways of teaching and learning. It enhances learning by providing a better understanding of the topic as well as motivating students" [Lari F. S., 2014]

1. The presence of PPT for teachers.

How teachers teach depends primarily on their knowledge and capacity and the materials they use. One of the most common teaching techniques is PPT, has several advantages. First of all, it saves the time of the tutors during the lessons and increases the efficiency because many educators spend more than half of the lesson finding materials for teaching. PPT is the basis of measures to prevent a such circumstance. Its importance is recognized by many people today. Such as: GISELLE CORBEIL (2007) says that "It cannot be denied, however, that, when it comes to class management, one of the advantages of PPTs is saving time. Time that is spent on the preparation of these PPTs outside the class is made up for by the time saved in the classroom by not having to write everything on the board. This means that it is almost inevitable that students using PPTs might occasionally be provided with more detailed explanations and more examples than those students using the textbook + blackboard" [Corbeil, Giselle, 2007].

Moreover, power point helps lecturer engage students, the particular reason for circumstance ppt include colorful contents that capture the attention of apprentice. It is more enjoyable for students than just listening to the teachers' explanation. EPE Syafril and W Kurniawati (2021) know that "PPT-audio becomes an alternative learning media. It can bring out and strengthen students' imagination, creativity, and motivation when they are learning, especially using interesting pictures and narration" [Syafril, E. P. E., and W. Kurniawati, 2021] I think this helps to reduce the number of student who falls asleep in the classroom. This can also be a factor in increasing the demand for power point in education.

Power point slides are very useful for distance learning. Teachers can effectively organize lessons by sharing PPT presentations on-screen during online classes or sending them to students in advance, since PPT slides contain images, videos, diagram, and text, students can easily study the lesson. Additionally, PPT presentations can be shared on online platforms.

2. Upsides of PPT for student

Presentations help improve several skills of students. Firstly, power enhances students' speaking skills because along with preparing the ppt, they are also required to present it. These aid students to overcome their inner fear when speaking in front of the class and increases their confidence and engagement. Furthermore, a power point presentation contributes to the development of students' creativity. This is because the person creating it must carefully select an appropriate design, videos, and images, as well as strategically plan their layout and distribution, which are crucial aspects of the process. Norasyikin Osman, Siti Salwa Mohd Noor, Nurazan Mohamad Rouyan, Norhayati Che Hat (2021) believe that "PowerPoint can be used to prepare slides in a more attractive and effective way which includes the integration of multimedia elements like texts, graphics, animation and video. It offers ready-to-use templates based on themes, colours or effects which users can easily select according to their needs" [Osman, Norasyikin, 2021]

¹ *Buriboev Jakhongir, SamSIFL, Payarik faculty teacher*

² *Abdimalikova Gavhar, 1st year student of SamSIFL, Payarik faculty*

3. Downsides of ppt

Every seemingly perfect things come with its own achievements as well as inherent flows. What I mean to say is that Power point also has its own drawbacks an inconvenience. Firstly, excessive reliance on power point can lead students to a dependence that ultimately undermines their comprehension and relations of the lesson. By overusing presentation, they may struggle to engage with the material on a deeper cognitive level, limiting their ability to think critically and apply knowledge independently. Beyond its impact on students, power point also presents certain disadvantages for educators. While it undeniably enhances efficiency by saving time and facilitating reusability it can inadvertently encourage teachers to rely on slides rather than their own expertise. This overdependence on pre prepared materials may hinder continuous professional growth, as educators become less inclined to revisit and refine their subject knowledge independently over time. Consequently, this stagnation in professional development poses a serious challenge to the overall quality of education.

Conclusion

All in all, it is very difficult to imagine online and offline teaching without ppt. The demand for PPT is very high nowadays its benefit is more than its harm. Because, as we mentioned above, the most important thing is that it prevented the wasting of time in class. For this reason, it is valuable, and I believe that it will not lose its value even now, because both teachers and students have fully adapted to it.

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